

Graphical and Statistical Communication Patterns of Automated Conversational Agents in Collaborative Computer-Mediated Communication Systems

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Abstract—Automated conversational agents, also known as “chatbots” or “chatterbots,” are computer programs used in a variety of collaborative communications systems, often for entertainment or business purposes. However, their use as malicious tools has more recently made them a growing nuisance and security concern. We present a detailed graphical and statistical analysis of communication patterns (specifically involving message sizes and inter-message delays) for improving the detection of automated conversational agents in collaborative computer-mediated communication systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conversational agents are automated natural language communication programs that interface with humans via real-time text-based computer-mediated communications (CMC). These programs are also known widely as “chatbots” or “chatterbots.” The use of conversational agents (hereafter referred to as “chatbots” or simply as “bots”) for entertainment, education, and business communications is growing in popularity and utility [1,2,3,4]. As the technology continues to progress in sophistication, bots will undoubtedly find emerging application in many other areas.

Unfortunately, chatbots are already finding application in the Internet’s underground. They are an increasing nuisance for chat, IM, and text-based CMC users, because of phishing attempts and through the spread of malware and spam [5,6,7]. More maliciously, they are being used as automated intelligence agents and scam artists, e.g., by attempting social engineering and teasing out personal information from users to be used for identity theft [8,9]. Bots can pose considerable security risks considering that they may be dispatched in virtually unlimited numbers and can work tirelessly at their goals, in contrast to individual humans attempting such feats in a person-to-person manner. To combat this threat, reliable methods for detecting bots are needed, so that malicious automated agents can be identified and removed from CMC systems.

Some previous and current attempts to stop chatbots from entering public chat rooms utilize CAPTCHAs (Automated Turing Tests) so that only humans can enter [e.g., 10], but this defense can be bypassed with human assistance. Keyword-based filtering and related spam detection methods are common but seem to be having limited success with chatbots. Gianvecchio et al. [11] suggested using metrics based upon gross communication patterns, such as communicators’ message sizes and inter-message delay times. Using a large dataset of public chat transcripts, they provided extensive evidence that chatbots could be classified into as many as 14 unique behavioral types based upon these metrics. And these metrics, when coupled with pattern-matching and/or machine-learning algorithms, could be extremely effective at distinguishing between humans and bots in computer-mediated communications. However, the chat data they analyzed was limited to public chat rooms with many multiple simultaneous communicators, and was primarily focused on bots that were attempting to get users to click on hyperlinks (either posted in messages or in their online profiles). It was unclear from their work whether similar chatbot behavioral patterns would be present in other types of CMC, such as one-on-one instant messaging, or when bots are attempting to carry on lengthy, convincing conversations with humans.

We attempted to study such questions in a previous work [12], using a different (and considerably smaller) dataset. We provided supporting evidence that the gross behavioral metrics suggested by Gianvecchio et al. (message sizes, inter-message delays) could be useful for passively distinguishing between humans and bots. In this work, we present a more detailed graphical and statistical analysis of related measures using a similar but larger data set.

II. METHOD

A. Chat Transcript Data Set

As in our previous work [12], we gathered our chat data from the publicly-available transcripts of the Loebner Prize in

Artificial Intelligence [13]. The Loebner Prize is a formal public Turing Test competition in which the world’s best chatbot programs compete to be the most “human” in terms of conversational capabilities. The Turing Test was suggested by British mathematician Alan Turing as a practical method for gauging the “intelligence” of an artificially-intelligent conversational agent [14]. The Test requires human judges to determine through text-based conversations whether their conversing partner is a human confederate or a computer program.

One of the great advantages of the Loebner Prize dataset is that the communicators are all unambiguously defined as either humans or chatbots; another is that an exceedingly large proportion of the conversations specifically involve chatbots, whereas other public chat datasets do not typically possess such high frequency of bot communications. Yet another advantage is that the bots are specifically trying to carry on human-like conversations with people for lengthy periods, whereas in many public data sets bots are mostly trying to convince users to click hyperlinks posted in their messages or in their online profiles [11].

A potential disadvantage of this dataset is that the conversational situation might not be considered “typical,” in that most of the human judges are suspicious as to the other communicators’ identities from the start, and many of the conversations might be rightly classified as “interrogations” as opposed to merely “normal, everyday conversations.” Nonetheless, since both the human participants (confederates) and bots faced similar interrogations by the human judges, we do not believe this to be a fatal flaw to our analyses and interpretations; indeed, in our previous work [12], there was little difference between the two human groups (judges and confederates) on the inter-message delay and message size distribution measures. In any case, the nature of our dataset is certainly a caveat to be kept in mind when interpreting our data and drawing conclusions.

Although in our previous work [12] we used data only from the 2008 competition, in this work we analyzed five separate competitions, from the years 1996, 1997, 2004, 2005, and again from 2008. These particular years were chosen for analysis -- instead of using all 15 years of available data -- for several reasons: these years’ data included text files, which allowed for ease of analysis; and these years included all the necessary and desired information for analysis of the transcripts, i.e., some years did not include clear delineation of individual communicator identities, time-stamping, structuring of conversations, etc.

This dataset captured a total of 9,206 messages in 254 brief conversations involving over 50 individual humans and 22 chatbots. It should be noted that some bots (and humans) were apparently repeat participants across two or more competition years.

B. Data Analysis Methods

From the raw transcript data, we calculated three primary metrics of interest: inter-message delay times (the time between sequential message transmissions), message size (the number of words transmitted per message), and message rate

(the message size divided by the inter-message delay, in words per minute or wpm; note that this measure is related but distinct from *typing speeds* which are also typically measured in words per minute). From these metrics, we analyzed features of the human and bot distributions, including central tendencies, dispersions, skewness, kurtosis, complexity, and visual analysis of distributions. Other statistical tests (i.e., ANOVA) are performed where appropriate, using $\alpha=0.05$.

Messaging complexity was measured via two methods: normalized entropy and normalized entropy rate. *Entropy* was calculated using Shannon’s information entropy approach [15], and can be interpreted in this context as the complexity of messaging behaviors. Entropy was measured by first calculating the empirical probability, $p(x_i)$, of occurrence of each inter-message delay, message size, and message rate. The probabilities for each category were then used in the Shannon entropy equation:

$$H(x_i) = -\sum(p(x_i) * \log(p(x_i)))$$

Entropy rate can be interpreted as the entropy of sequential pairs of observations. For our purposes, high entropy rates would suggest a highly complex messaging process. Similar to above, the empirical probability, $p(x_{ij})$, was calculated for each sequential pair of observations (i,j) in the inter-message delays, message sizes, and message rates. It is similar in form and calculation to the entropy calculation:

$$H(x_{ij}) = -\sum(p(x_{ij}) * \log(p(x_{ij})))$$

Due to the fact that these measures are sensitive to sample size, we normalized our calculations of both the entropies and the entropy rates (giving values from 0 to 100%). Normalization was accomplished by taking the observed entropy (or entropy rate) divided by the maximum possible entropy (or entropy rate) given the sample size, n :

$$\text{Normalized } H(x_i) = -\sum(p(x) * \log(p(x)) / \log(n))$$

These normalized entropy and entropy rates provided measures of complexity that could more be easily compared across the varying the sample sizes used in these analyses.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Inter-Message Delay Times

Overall results concerning inter-message delay times are presented in Table I; further results are presented and discussed in the text and associated figures.

TABLE I. INTER-MESSAGE DELAYS

Measures	Humans	Bots
Mean (arithmetic)	20.4	7.3
Median	17.5	4.0
Standard Deviation	13.6	9.2
Skewness	0.793	2.183
Kurtosis	-0.074	5.800
Sample size (n)	5424	3527

Figure 1. Inter-message delay relative frequency distributions for humans and chatbots. Inter-message delays were measured in seconds.

Figure 2. The same data as in Fig. 1, but plotted on logarithmic X and Y axes. The bulk of the human data points (almost 75%) fall nearly on a straight line (the dashed grey line).

1) *Central Tendencies and Dispersions*: Average human inter-message delay times were substantially longer in comparison to bots (20.4 versus 7.3 seconds, respectively). Median values produced a similar pattern (17.5 versus 4.0 seconds, respectively). Variability for the human inter-message delays was also noticeably larger (standard deviations of 13.6 versus 9.2 seconds).

2) *Distribution Shapes*: Measures of distribution shapes were also noticeably different between humans and bots. Human inter-message delay distribution skewness was measured at 0.793 (with a standard error of skewness of 0.033), while the bot distribution skewness was measured at 2.183 (with a standard error of skewness of 0.041). Human inter-message delay distribution kurtosis was measured at -0.074 (with a standard error of kurtosis of 0.066). Bot distribution kurtosis was measured at 5.800 (with a standard error of kurtosis of 0.082).

3) *Graphical Analysis*: As can be seen in Fig. 1, human inter-message delays follow a distinctly different distribution pattern than bots. To allow a more straightforward comparison to the results of Gianvecchio et al. [11], we also plotted the inter-message delay distributions on log-log scales in Fig. 2. The advantage of this plotting method is that a power law distribution (which we would expect to find for the humans) tends to reveal itself as a linear pattern when plotted on log-log scales. Just as Gianvecchio et al. found, the bulk of the human data points (inter-message delays of 10 s or greater comprise almost 75% of the distribution) fall nearly on a straight line in this log-log plot; the same is not quite true for the bots.

4) *Discussion*: Inter-message delay times seemed to offer a variety of distinguishing measures for detecting bot versus human chat communications. At least in our dataset, potentially useful metrics involving inter-message delays included: measures of central tendency, dispersion or variability, skewness, and kurtosis. These results directly support our previous work in [12], the results of Gianvecchio

et al. [11], and other human chat data [16] demonstrating temporal patterns in human communication that can be used to distinguish them from chatbots. Further, these results indirectly support other research showing that humans exhibit distinct temporal patterns in virtually all forms of their communications, including asynchronous CMC such as blogging, texting, cyber forums, e-mailing, and even non-CMC including surveys and spoken communication [17].

B. Message Sizes

Overall results concerning message sizes are presented in Table II; further results are presented and discussed in the text and associated figures.

1) *Central Tendencies and Dispersions*: Average human message sizes were only slightly smaller than bots (8.4 versus 9.3 word count per message, respectively). Median values produced a similar pattern (6.0 versus 7.0, respectively). Variability, too, was very similar between humans and bots (standard deviations of 7.8 versus 8.6 words per message).

2) *Distribution Shapes*: Measures of distribution shapes were somewhat mixed on whether there was a noticeable difference between humans and bots. Human message size distribution skewness was measured at 3.077 (with a standard error of skewness of 0.033), while the bot distribution skewness was measured at 2.603 (with a standard error of skewness of 0.041), suggesting little difference on this measure. However, human message size distribution kurtosis was measured at 17.213 (with a standard error of kurtosis of 0.066) while bot distribution kurtosis was measured at 12.464 (with a standard error of kurtosis of 0.081), which may suggest a possible distinguishing metric.

3) *Graphical Analysis*: As can be seen in Fig. 3, human and bot message size distributions are highly similar and practically indistinguishable.

TABLE II. MESSAGE SIZES

Measures	Humans	Bots
Mean (arithmetic)	8.4	9.3
Median	6.0	7.0
Standard Deviation	7.8	8.6
Skewness	3.077	2.603
Kurtosis	17.213	12.464
Sample size (n)	5586	3620

Figure 3. Message size relative frequency distributions for humans and chatbots. Message sizes were measured in word count per message.

4) *Discussion*: Analysis of message sizes offered very little in terms of distinguishing between humans and bots. This result is in contrast to our previous findings (with a smaller sample) that suggested message sizes to possibly be a distinguishing metric [12]. This result is also somewhat in conflict with the results of Gianvecchio et al [11] who found many “types” of bots whose message size distribution shapes differed widely from the observed human distributions. Even though in our sample there was a statistically significant difference between human and bot message sizes ($F=34.95$, $p<.001$), the statistical effect size was near zero (partial- $\eta^2=.004$). Indeed, visual inspection of the relative frequency distributions of human versus bot message sizes shows extensive overlap and similarity of distribution shapes between the groups, and both distributions appear to follow an exponential decay (after excluding the initial spikes).

C. Message rates

Overall results concerning message rates are presented in Table III; further results are presented and discussed in the text and associated figures.

1) *Central Tendencies and Dispersions*: Average human message rates were measured at a reasonable 35.7 words per minute (median of 24.0 wpm), while average bot message rates were a blistering 145.4 words per minute (median of 72.0

TABLE III. MESSAGE RATES

Measures	Humans	Bots
Mean (arithmetic)	35.7	145.4
Median	24.0	72.0
Standard Deviation	67.4	233.4
Skewness	10.36	4.72
Kurtosis	151.46	31.90
Sample size (n)	5364	2805

Figure 4. Message rate relative frequency distributions for humans and chatbots. Message rates were measured in words per minute (wpm).

wpm). Variability, too, was widely different between the two groups. The standard deviation of human message rates was surprisingly large at 67.4 wpm, but bots were even larger at 233.4 wpm.

2) *Distribution Shapes*: Distribution shape measurements regarding message rates suggest large differences between the groups. Human distribution skewness was measured at 10.358 (standard error of skewness was 0.033), while bot skewness was 4.720 (standard error of skewness was 0.046). Human distribution kurtosis was 151.460 wpm (standard error of kurtosis was 0.067) versus bot kurtosis of 31.901 (standard error of 0.092).

3) *Graphical Analysis*: As can be seen in Fig. 4, human and bot message rate distributions are distinctly different. Almost all of the observed human message rates fall below 70 wpm, with a large spike peaking at about 20 wpm. In contrast, bot message rates are scattered with a flat, wide, and irregularly-shaped distribution. All observed message rates are shown in Fig. 5, and median message rates for individual humans and bots is plotted in Fig. 6. The differences between humans and chatbots in regards to message rates are clearly evident in both of these figures.

4) *Discussion*: Message rate, a combined measure of inter-message delays and message sizes, seems to offer yet another way to distinguish between human and chatbot communications. Useful message rate metrics found in our

Figure 5. All observed message rates in words per minute (wpm). Notice the y-axis is a logarithmic scale to accommodate extreme observations. Each mark is a single observation for humans or chatbots. The thick dotted horizontal line indicates a cut-off message rate that captures 90.4% of the humans and excludes 60.4% of the bots (between 0 and 70 wpm, inclusive).

Figure 6. Median message rates per individual, in words per minute (wpm). Notice the y-axis is a logarithmic scale to accommodate extreme values. Each mark is the median of observations for an individual human or chatbot. The shaded grey region indicates the median message rates that include 100% of the humans and exclude 78% of the bots (between 5 and 50 wpm).

data include means, standard deviations, skewness, and kurtosis. Had we attempted bot detection in our dataset by using a simple rule that included only median message rates of individual communicators that fell within the typical human range (5 to 50 wpm), we would have been able to quite easily detect and remove 78% of the bots while excluding no humans. Another simple rule that excluded individual messages with rates above 70 wpm would have included 90.4% of the human messages, while excluding 60.4% of the bot messages.

D. Messaging Complexity

1) *Entropy*: Analysis of the normalized messaging entropies revealed some differences between human and bot communication entropy. Entropies were calculated per individual communicator. Results are shown in Table IV. As would be expected if humans demonstrated more complexity in their communications than bots, humans showed higher entropies on all three measures. The individual human entropies were 1.7 times higher than bots on the inter-message delays (Fig. 7), 1.4 times higher on message sizes (Fig. 9), and 1.3 times higher on message rates (Fig. 11). Here, the pattern of results is the same as those of Gianvecchio et al. [11], who found the messaging complexities (as measured by the corrected conditional entropies) to be higher for humans in both inter-message delays and message sizes (they did not analyze message rates). Visual analysis of these distributions (Fig. 7, 9, and 11, top row, next page) offers a clear distinction between humans and bots, particularly on the inter-message delay and message rate entropies.

2) *Entropy Rate*: Analysis of the normalized messaging entropy rates also revealed large differences between human and bot communications. Averages of the individual entropy rate results are shown in Table V. Humans on average exhibited substantially higher entropy rates (i.e., complexity) on all three messaging behaviors. The human inter-message delay entropy rates were on average 2.4 times higher than bots (Fig. 8), message size were 1.6 times higher (Fig. 10), and message rates 1.3 times higher (Fig. 12). These results also support the findings of Gianvecchio et al. [11], who also examined the entropy rates of inter-message delays and message sizes. Visual analysis of the distributions (Fig. 8, 10, and 12, lower row, next page) again shows clear distinctions between humans and bots.

TABLE IV. MEAN INDIVIDUAL NORMALIZED ENTROPY

Normalized Entropy (%)	Humans	Chatbots
Inter-Message Delay	80.1	46.3
Message Size	76.9	56.9
Message Rate	82.8	64.6

TABLE V. MEAN INDIVIDUAL NORMALIZED ENTROPY RATE

Normalized Entropy Rate (%)	Humans	Chatbots
Inter-Message Delay	58.0	18.4
Message Size	46.3	19.3
Message Rate	61.9	35.1

Figure 7. Individual inter-message delay entropy (normalized). Each mark is the observed entropy of an individual human or chatbot.

Figure 9. Individual message size entropy (normalized). Each mark is the observed entropy of an individual human or chatbot.

Figure 11. Individual message rate entropy (normalized). Each mark is the observed entropy of an individual human or chatbot.

Figure 8. Individual inter-message delay entropy rates (normalized). Each mark is the observed entropy rate of an individual human or chatbot.

Figure 10. Individual message size entropy rates (normalized). Each mark is the observed entropy rate of an individual human or chatbot.

Figure 12. Individual message rate entropy rates (normalized). Each mark is the observed entropy rate of an individual human or chatbot.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Despite the nature of our dataset in comparison to others [e.g., 11], our results generally support the utility of chat communication metrics for distinguishing between human and bot communications. Specifically, we found that measures of central tendency, dispersion, distribution shapes, and related patterns of inter-message delays were very distinct between humans and bots. Further, we found that message rates, a derived measure from both inter-message delays and message sizes, could also be of some utility. Our entropy and entropy rate measurements suggested that individual bots generally exhibit lower complexity than individual humans in their chat communications, and this was true for inter-message delays, message sizes, and message rates. However, the statistical and distributional analysis of message sizes seemed to offer few metrics that might aid in the identification of bot communications.

Future research into differentiating metrics for humans and bots might include the analysis of keystroke dynamics,

alternative measures of complexity, and other graphical and/or statistical patterns of chat, including word choice/phraseology, typographical error distributions, detailed chronemic analysis, conversational dynamics, etc. We plan on developing visualization tools for chatbot detection that specifically focus on some of the metrics discussed in this work. We are also considering the development of a set of “humanness” metrics for rating the conversational capabilities of chatbots, which may also be advantageously visualized for chat users, chat room administrators, and AI developers.

Chatbots will conceivably continue to progress in sophistication until their conversational capabilities are virtually indistinguishable from humans. In the future, we will find these automated conversational agents in a variety of unforeseen applications, in addition to their current growing applications in commerce, education, and entertainment. However, malicious chatbots can pose considerable security risks since they can be unleashed in virtually unlimited numbers and can work tirelessly on gathering intelligence, spreading malware and spam, and generally hampering

effective collaborations and communications. As bots approach the communication level of an average human, their capability to be used as malevolent tools will also grow. We hope the analysis and discussion presented herein provides improved capabilities to detect and remove malicious automated conversational agents from collaborative computer-mediated communication systems, so that such systems can be used efficiently, effectively, and securely for their intended purposes.

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